

Impact of Basic Life Support Training Program among Saudi Primary School Teachers in Riyadh

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Abstract

Introduction: Basic Life Support (BLS) training plays a crucial role in equipping individuals to provide immediate emergency care until medical help is available. In the school setting, where injuries are common among students, teachers serve as primary caregivers and first responders. This study aimed to assess the impact of BLS training on the resuscitation knowledge and skills of primary school teachers in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.

Methods: A randomized interventional trial was conducted with 48 primary school teachers, aged 23 to 50 years. After providing a concise BLS training program, participants completed a pre-and post-test questionnaire assessing their understanding of resuscitation techniques. Descriptive statistics and chi-square tests were used for data analysis.

Results: Before the BLS training, the participants demonstrated limited knowledge and skills in resuscitation techniques. For instance, only 20.8% correctly identified the ideal compression depth, and 33.3% were unsure about the ideal steps for Basic Life Support. However, after the training, a significant improvement was observed in participants' knowledge and skills, with a higher percentage answering correctly in the post-training questionnaire (e.g., 87.5% correctly identified the recommended compression rate, and 75% accurately identified the ideal steps for Basic Life Support).

More Information

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Basic life support, BLS, training, life support program, teachers, primary schools.

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Conclusion: This study highlights the positive impact of BLS training on the resuscitation knowledge and skills of primary school teachers in Riyadh. Primary school teachers can enhance emergency response capabilities and contribute to student safety, by providing teachers with the necessary knowledge and practical skills. These findings emphasize the importance of implementing targeted training programs in schools to improve resuscitation education for teachers.

Introduction

Cardiac arrest as defined by the American Heart Association and the American College of Cardiology is sudden arrest of cardiac activity so that the victim becomes unresponsive, with no normal breathing and no signs of circulation [1]. If corrective measures are not taken rapidly, this condition progresses to sudden death [2].

Basic Life Support (BLS) refers to the immediate emergency care administered to an injured person by trained individuals, either medical or non-medical until professional medical help is available [3]. In the event of cardiac arrest, basic life support can be effective to reduce the chance of death [4]. The main objectives of first aid are to save lives, prevent the situation from worsening, and facilitate recovery. The initial actions taken to manage injuries and common illnesses can significantly impact the future course of the condition and the likelihood of complications [5]. Recognizing the importance of early first aid training, there is a growing emphasis on educating individuals about first aid during the early stages of their education worldwide. By adequately preparing and educating students, they have the potential to positively influence the overall health status of society [6,7].

Schools provide an ideal setting for teaching students about first aid due to the extensive amount of time children spend there, engaging in various activities that contribute to their physical and mental development [8]. It has been reported that 88% of injuries in children are physical in nature, with nearly 20% of these injuries occurring during school hours. In fact, injuries sustained during school hours, particularly during extracurricular activities, tend to be more severe compared to incidents outside of school [9]. As schoolchildren are still developing physically and mentally, they are more susceptible to various risks and require first aid assistance more frequently than adults [10].

These injuries often occur during sports activities or while participating in extracurricular activities such as cycling, swimming, and games. Schoolteachers play a vital role as primary caregivers and the first responders in emergency situations at school [11]. Their role complements that of parents, and they are responsible for managing health-related situations for both healthy children and those with special healthcare needs. Equipping schoolteachers with knowledge, awareness, and practical skills in first aid and BLS can empower them to provide appropriate care during emergencies.

By providing teachers with this knowledge and skill set, they become a crucial resource for students, helping them to understand and apply first aid principles [12,13]. Most of all cardiac deaths are sudden and usually unexpected, which has proven to be uniformly fatal in the past [14,15]. However, bystander cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) and advances within emergency medical services (EMS) have proven life-saving interventions [16,17,18]. Despite this, approximately 10% of those suffering from cardiac arrest leave the hospital alive, most of which are neurologically impaired [19].

It is vital for healthcare providers to raise awareness and promote first aid education in schools in order to protect children from exacerbating their conditions and provide initial care until professional medical attention is available [20,21]. However, it is important to ensure that individuals providing first aid possess sufficient knowledge and practical experience to effectively decrease the risk of injury and save lives.

Methods

In our trial, we utilized a randomized design to investigate the knowledge and skills of primary school teachers in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia regarding resuscitation techniques. The study was conducted over a period of one year, from November 2022 to December 2023.

Study Participants

A total of 48 primary school teachers were included in the study, with participants selected based on their age range of 23 to 50 years. Intermediate and high school teachers were excluded from the study.

Study Questionnaire

Prior to the study, all participants provided informed consent, indicating their willingness to participate. The data collection process involved the administration of a pre-and post-test questionnaire, which was completed using a traditional pen and paper format. The questionnaire consisted of six questions that assessed various aspects of resuscitation knowledge and skills, including compression rate, cessation of resuscitation efforts, chest compression depth, familiarity with automated external defibrillators, proper CPR steps, and confidence in performing hands-only CPR on a patient in cardiac arrest.

To ensure the validity and reliability of the questionnaire, a pre-testing phase was conducted with a small sample of teachers. Based on feedback received during this pre-testing phase, minimal changes were

made to the questionnaire before its administration to the larger study sample.

Statistical Analysis

Data analysis was performed using descriptive statistics, specifically frequencies and chi-square tests, to examine the responses provided by participants. Additionally, a six-point scale was employed to assess the participants' level of resuscitation knowledge and skills. The statistical software SPSS version 25 was utilized to carry out the data analysis.

Sample Size

Sample size determination was performed after a power analysis (power = 0.8; β = 0.2; α = 0.02) using PASS software (PASS 2023, NCSS LLC, Kaysville, UT). Standard Deviation (SD) and the impact of basic life support was taken from a previous (19) study. These data were used for the sample size equation: $n = 2[(Z\beta + Z\alpha) \sigma / \Delta]^2$, where n (sample size in the study group) = 36; α = 0.05; $Z\alpha$ = 1.96; β = 0.2; $Z\beta$ = 0.84; σ (estimated SD based on similar studies) = 1.4; and Δ = the estimated effect size– 1. After matching the inclusion and exclusion criteria and considering a possible 10% dropout, 48 primary schoolteachers will be required to find a statistically significant correlation in basic life support.

Ethical Approval

Ethical considerations were of utmost importance in this study. All participants provided informed consent, while an approval letter from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) was obtained. Steps were taken to ensure the confidentiality and privacy of participants' data throughout the study.

By conducting this study, we aimed to gain insights into the level of resuscitation knowledge and skills among primary school teachers in Riyadh. The findings of this study will contribute to a better understanding of the

current state of resuscitation education in schools and may help inform the development of targeted training programs to improve teachers' ability to respond effectively in urgent situations.

Results

Forty-eight participants were involved and filled out our questionnaire resulting in 96 responses. The most frequent age group was (31-40) years. All study participants, except two, held a bachelor for an academic degree. No baseline statistical differences were found among different age categories.

Regarding the pre-training responses, 23 teachers answered the first question as "About 50", while 18 chose "I don't know". Only 7 teachers chose the answer "100-120". Fifty-two percent of participants answered the second question which asked about the duration of cardiopulmonary compressions as "Until medical professionals take over". About the ideal depth for each compression, only 10 participants (20.8%) chose "At least 5 cm". The most frequent answer was "I don't know" (50%).

Question 4 asked about the defibrillator function, and the answers were "performs CPR, dials 911 and restarts the heart" (35.4%), "I don't know" (33.3%), "shocks the heart and restarts the heart to normal rhythm" (29.1%), and "automatically dials 911 and calls for help" (2.1%). Question 5 asked about the ideal steps for BLS, and the answers were as follows; 35.4% of study participants chose "Push hard and fast in the center of the chest then dial 911", 16 (33.3%) chose "I don't know", 10 (20.8%) chose "Dial 911, push hard and fast in the center of the chest", and 5 (10.4%) teachers answered, "Give two breaths then dial 911". Twenty-two of the study participants answered "No" for having the trust to perform hands-only CPR for a patient with cardiac arrest. See Table 1 for the pre-training responses.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Study Participants, Pre and Post Training Survey Responses, and Difference from Baseline

Age group (years)		(N)	(%)			
20-30		1	2.1			
31-40		33	68.8			
41-50		13	27.1			
51-60		1	2.1			
Academic degree						
Bachelor's degree		45	93.8			
Master's degree		3	6.3			
Age group (years)						
		pre-training survey responses	Post-training survey responses			
Parameter/ question		(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	p-value†
Question 1						
I don't know		18	37.5	0	0	<0.001
About 50		23	47.9	2	4.2	
100-120		7	14.6	42	87.5	

	130-150	0	0.0	4	8.3	
Question 2						
	I don't know	13	27.1	0	0.0	<0.001
	5 minutes	7	14.6	2	4.2	
	15 minutes	3	6.3	2	4.2	
	Until medical professionals take over	25	52.1	44	91.7	
Question 3						
	I don't know	19	39.6	0	0.0	<0.001
	at least 1 cm	6	12.5	1	2.1	
	at least 3 cm	13	27.1	2	4.2	
	at least 5 cm	10	20.8	45	93.8	
Question 4						
	I don't know	16	33.3	0	0.0	<0.001
	Automatically dials 911 and calls for help	2	4.2	3	6.3	
	Performs CPR, dials 911 and restarts the heart	16	33.3	11	22.9	
	Shocks the heart and restarts the heart to normal rhythm	14	29.2	34	70.8	
Question 5						
	I don't know	16	33.3	1	2.1	<0.001
	Dial 911, push hard and fast in the center of the chest	10	20.8	36	75.0	
	Push hard and fast in the center of the chest then dial 911	17	35.4	11	22.9	
	Give tow breaths then dial 911	5	10.4	0	0.0	
Question 6						
	No	26	54.2	7	14.6	<0.001
	Yes	22	45.8	41	85.4	
Note: n= Number of responses in each item; %= Percentage of responses; †= Significant difference for the correct answer in each item from the pre-training response.						

Regarding the post-training responses, the majority of the study participants (87.5%) chose the answer “100-120”, while only 6 teachers answered incorrectly “About 50” or “130-150”. After our BLS training, nearly all teachers (93.8%) answered the second question “Until medical professionals take over”. Forty- five participants chose “At least 5 cm” as the correct answer for question 3. The post-training answers for question 4 were “shocks and reset the heart to normal rhythm” (70.8%), “performs CPR, dials 911 and restarts the heart” (25%), and “automatically dials 911 and calls for help” (4.1%).

Answers for question 5 were as follows; 36 (75%) chose “Dial 911, push hard and fast in the center of the chest”, 11 (22.9%) answered “Push hard and fast in the center of the chest then dial 911” and 1 (2.1%) teacher chose “I don't know”. Forty-one participants answered “Yes” as they had the trust to perform hands-only CPR for an

individual with an arrested heart. A statistically significant difference was found among the percentages of the correct answers for all survey questions with all p-values <0.05. See Table 1 for the post-training responses.

Discussion

Findings Summary

The findings of this study indicate that there is a significant improvement in the resuscitation knowledge and skills of primary school teachers in Riyadh after undergoing Basic Life Support (BLS) training. The post-training responses showed a higher percentage of correct answers compared to the pre-training responses for all survey questions. This suggests that the BLS training program was effective in enhancing the participants' understanding of resuscitation techniques.

Figure 1: The Post-Training Responses after the BLS Program

Figure 2: Distribution of Age Groups among the Study Participants

Figure 3: Difference in the Correct Responses after the BLS Training Program

Our Results in the Context of Literature

In comparing our results with other publications on the same topic, it is important to note that there is a growing emphasis on educating individuals about first aid and basic life support (BLS) during the early stages of their education worldwide. This aligns with our study's objective of assessing the level of resuscitation knowledge and skills among primary school teachers in Riyadh [22,23]. Our findings indicate that there is room for improvement in teachers' knowledge and skills related to resuscitation techniques. For example, in the pre-training responses, only 20.8% of participants correctly chose the ideal compression depth of at least 5 cm, while 50% responded with 'I don't know.' Similarly, 33.3% of participants were unsure about the ideal steps for BLS [24]. These results highlight the need for targeted training programs to enhance teachers' ability to respond effectively in urgent situations.

When comparing our results with other publications, it is important to consider the context and sample size of each study. Our study involved 48 participants, all of whom were primary school teachers in Riyadh [25]. While our findings provide valuable insights into the resuscitation knowledge and skills of this specific group, they may not be representative of teachers in other regions or educational levels. Therefore, it would be beneficial to conduct similar studies with larger sample sizes and diverse populations to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of the current state of resuscitation education in schools [3].

Furthermore, it is worth noting that our study utilized a pre-and post-test questionnaire to assess participants' knowledge and skills. This approach allows for the evaluation of the effectiveness of the BLS training program provided to the teachers [26]. By comparing the pre-training and post-training responses, we observed significant improvements in participants' knowledge and skills. For example, after the training, the majority of teachers correctly answered the question about the duration of cardiopulmonary compressions as 'Until medical professionals take over.' Additionally, a higher percentage of participants chose the correct answers for questions related to defibrillator function and the ideal steps for BLS.

Points of Strength and Limitations

One of the strengths of this study is the randomized design, which allowed for a more rigorous evaluation of the effectiveness of the BLS training program. Additionally, the use of a pre-and post-test questionnaire provided a comprehensive assessment of the participants' resuscitation knowledge and skills. However, there are some limitations to consider. Firstly, the study sample size was relatively small, with only 50 primary school teachers included. This may limit the generalizability of the findings to a larger

population. Secondly, the study was conducted in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other geographical locations. Further research with larger sample sizes and more diverse populations is needed to validate these findings.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the results of this study demonstrate that BLS training can significantly improve the resuscitation knowledge and skills of primary school teachers in Riyadh. By providing teachers with the necessary knowledge and practical skills, they can effectively respond to emergencies at school and contribute to the overall health and safety of students. These findings highlight the importance of incorporating first aid and BLS training programs in schools to ensure the well-being of students and prevent complications in emergency situations. Further research is needed to explore the long-term effects of BLS training and to develop targeted training programs for teachers in different educational settings.

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